

Roman Science Inspired by Emerging JWST Results: [website](#), [proceedings](#), [video](#)

Session 2 live-captioning, Tuesday 20 June 2023:

[Surveys of the very nearby universe](#)

Sam Grunblatt: Exoplanet Science with JWST & Roman, A Journey through Space and Time

Okay I think we can start the session for this afternoon. It was my pleasure to introduce you to our next speaker, and he will talk about Exoplanet Science with JWST and Roman. Okay great. Great. Can everyone hear me okay? All right. I'm sorry to report that I do not have any musical accompaniment to go along with this presentation. It is to be quite as awesome as what we just heard but I do my best to keep this entertaining. So for those of you who do not know me, I am Sam and I am a research scientist across the street at Johns Hopkins University, in a previously I was at the American National history Museum, and then I got my PhD at the University of Hawaii 2019. Enough about me, let's jump into Exoplanet Science with JWST & Roman. Okay, here we go beautiful. So, as my title says, this is a journey through space and time. So we will start with a journey through time here. Here we are looking at planet mass, versus orbital. As a function of time you can see the years going by there. First we only knew about our solar system within a 1995 we found a whole bunch more of these excellent planets, then under 2,000 we found a first transiting Exoplanet. And as time has gone on, the rest of the decade, what we know about X Exoplanet has really exploded. We have over 4,000 planets and I think it comes up to now 6,000 and so I will note that the colors here also correspond to different detection methods. And so, I will go through all of those except for imaging because I think that when a straightforward and a year hear about that in the couple talks from now. But, the history of Exoplanet starts with the late radio did the velocity detection method. So this is where were basically looking at the wobble of the stars is pulling back and forth, as the planet orbits around the star. And this actually requires a lot of photons because you're taking psychopathy. So was by ground-based facilities. But then over the last decade or 15 years or so, the most planets were detected using the transit method. In this required precise preterm entry with an interruption. This means that transit surveys were dominated by space facilities. So, once we discover transiting planets in the first home was discovered in the year 2,000, actually give us the first opportunity to see into planetary atmospheres. So with the Hubble space telescope with it Observatory up planet in transit but on multiple wavelengths. Say can see how the star on the planet appearance changed in to show us that slightly differently, you can see on the right here

we can see the wavelength. In certain atmospheres features can cause changes in the size of the problems that we see. And, once the 1st transit planet have been discovered. They give us a great opportunity to actually study the atmosphere right from the start's only two years after we have found the first transiting planet. We were able to confirm that it did have a atmosphere with the not so great plot that we have here but basically the idea is that if you look from the top that is the wavelength and you can see that once they've been those wavelength this feature at around 589 nanometers due to sodium get the planet a slightly different radius and that particular wavelength than on the other wavelengths. So that told us that there was something in the planets atmosphere so it looked a little bit different in that particular wavelength due to sodium admission. Since then, we've been very instrumental in revealing the diversity in the planetary atmosphere. So back in 2015 David make this plot which basically showed wildly knew about Exoplanet atmospheres of the time. We can see is that there may be only obtain a handful of systems and they have different set of properties that one can observe and from all of these measurements, you can see these admission features that I've mentioned, also some water features in between one and 2 microns. This also signs of clouds and hazes and those are the ramps up so you're seeing on the left side of the plot. But I also would like to point out that the data pass 1.6 microns on the slot and it's pretty limiting. And so, we have not had too many chances to understand a planetary atmosphere in the infrared. Meanwhile, transit detection has totally exploded thanks to K2 Kepler. So again this is showing other planets that we know of in 2020. And you can see that basically below ten S&S is on the spot, essentially all of those yellow dots are from Kepler, so they really revolutionize our understanding of smaller planets with thousands of newer planet discoveries. In this action reveal new features of planet demographics. So probably the most famous is the radius cap which is a lack of planets between 1.6 and around 2.2 earth radii. And that is basically the boundary between the rocky super earth, and gaseous sub Neptune worlds. And actually with an enhanced follow-up and better parameters from other similar missions we can actually get ages for the system and show that at young ages, the sub Neptune said to get more common in their little bit larger but over a timescale they can actually lose their atmospheres ended up turning into the super earth so the ratio of these two types of planet become similar. They result. And this is really transformative. Because Kepler made a popular first to determine planet occurrence rates. They showed a steps while planets are much more common than large ones. At least on a main sequence stars. And there's roughly uniform with a lot of the order. Period. The reuse is to determine around ten to 20% of all stars and earthlike planets. Which is a really excited results. We use K2 and test to extend that beyond the main sequence. So here we are looking a results of our planet occurrence about white dwarves as well as red giant stars as well. One of the things we were able to then do you see the slight differences in planet occurrence which provided new insights into how they evolved. Shockingly show a step planets can survive around white doors or it may reborn easily at stellar evolution. We also learn about planetary atmospheres from these missions. In this give us evidence that hot gas like planet can become inflated around their host stars, and I can be over time. But also that the hottest planets around the stars are actually less inflated than they expected. At very high masses which teaches us something about the heat and the energy transport in planetary atmospheres. Because I was great, the things of gotten kicked up a notch in the last couple of years. So JW ST launched on Christmas in 2021, and it has been revolutionizing the field of exoplanet atmospheres ever since. So this is

the distribution that is been submitted and accepted proposals for JWST for the general observing program. And you can see accounted for for almost a third of it. Beating out all other categories excepted and almost beating galaxies in the total time allotted as well. And the JWST Exoplanet results has made quite a splash since then. So much so that they were the cover story of nature magazine in February of this year. And with good reason. So, just look at the spectrum from wasp 39, a hot Jupiter that was observed by Exoplanet Science with JWST & Roman JWST. Elicit the colors here and we can actually resolve into their component in the molecular species that causes it. And so, just for reference, I'm going to put what we had from HSC, overlaid in a similar wavelength, you can see the optimal features in the sodium line, we had already seen, but essentially everything red weight of 1 micron was more brand-new. In this had one of the more interesting aspects of the planetary atmosphere. And the addition to the detected admissions, JWST detected equilibrium features of water and carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide in clouds is very high volumes. In addition it detected this lesson expected disequilibrium XO to feature, right around 4 microns. Page here. And that feature actually indicated that photo chemistries occurring in the atmosphere of this planet. In another exciting pieces this is that this equilibrium nature Esso to makes it a more precise constraints on the planetary atmosphere than just those equally grand for each species where the specs and changes are more subtle. So here's the feature versus CO₂ and H₂O. So I'm really excited to see how many more detections of this equilibrium chemistry unexpected chemistry James is going to find on these different Jupiters. And beyond hot Jupiter analysis, JWST can detect similar spectral features in much smaller planets. So we can search for atmospheres escaped and are now Neptune size planet as well. That'll inform our understanding of their atmospheres over time in the case of POSTNET's ecosystems, for instance the atmospheres escaped of a planet that is shrinking, so the model in Orange, should be measurably less than the atmosphere note product what's growing in size. So that a lettuce probe which of these models actually describe how these planets are evolving over time. And then JWST can go further than that, they can study the atmospheres of rocky planets. So, unfortunately no such planet has been found, so here I'm just showing the results from JWST observations of chapters one, B, C, and neither one shows any signs of a earthlike atmosphere which is shown by the curves at the bottom here. So most likely these are just bare rocks. But again this is only the beginning. There are tens of more rocky planets that are already scheduled to be observed. JWST is also transforming our ability to understand planet transformation. So here's a side-by-side picture of the young star. In the actual level of detail in is pretty astounding in their multiple gaps you can see this misalignment of the inner and outer disk and actually they used to be potential signs of a planet in the HST data which is been ruled out but they their new evidences of these disk cloud collisions and might have been found in this data. Finally JW came categorize planets that have been found nearby such as this one. VHS 1256B. The spectrum of this widely separated planetary mass companion is detections of sodium potassium and water and carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide and methane and 17 clouds. So there is you know all throughout the spectrum even though it's hard to see here this scale, physically all of that signal. And there's very little noise in the spectrum. So the various features back features are due to the different factors. So JWST is characterizing a more diverse set of planets than what was ever possible before. Not only are we getting a standard hot Jupiter's, but we can go to rocky planets are young systems old systems it's all really powerful. But Roman is can it take this even further by

detecting a larger and even more diverse as groups of planets that we have ever found before. And so, to take everyone back to their S.A.T. prep courses, through an analogy at the top of the slide, were wrong then is to JWST, what Kepler was the HST. So Roman really is a demographic Smiths machine. In the discovery will complement the details following up. Done a number of system with some bike stars, Romanesque geometry will be able to do a whole bunch of things we can detect orders of magnitude and more ground towards a more free-floating planets with romance in order of magnitude transiting planets as well. We have new targets for imaging will hear about a little bit. And again, as geometry that will be able to do will constrain the existence of cool gas like planet by a factor of five more bigger than Gaia. And like I said, were going to get lots and lots of planets working to those demographics. And, the key to that will basically be the Roman constructive bulge time survey. So this is basically a survey of the galactic center. And just like this video is suing you, the field of view is around 2.2 square degrees, covered with the 50 minute cadence over 6270 Tuesday season's over five years. That means were gonna monitor tens of millions of stars we can detect these transit events. The first time will be sensitive to planet populations beyond the parsecs from the sun. And to give you an idea of the propose fields for that galactic survey, these are going to be seven adjacent pointing in the window to clear the window towards the galactic center. And thanks to previous studies you actually can detect planets in this regime of the region of the galaxy. In the study has been optimized to try and produce as many gravitational microlensing events or detections as possible. And so, just to talk a little bit more about how microlensing works, so microlensing planets, is detected through the microlensing tech needs and those of the dark blue point in the slot. A can see that they occupy a larger region of parameter space. Lighter separation than a lot of the transiting planets for example. And actually at lower masses that we can say otherwise. And then part of that is because of how these lengths are detected. So essentially the way that microlensing works is that you have one star that happens in front of another star, and that it will effectively lends that that Grant Starck making it increase in brightness and then if you have another planet that is in orbit around that lens it'll cause a secondary increase in brightness that we can actually see and measure. Send a figure appear on the right you can send a C the white curve of the micro event that and what it looks like the ring affects vacancy -- -- but essentially the entire microlensing event takes onto the three months of one star passing in front of the other. But the little bump that you get on the event -- the microlensing event you get this overall shape but then you see you get this little blip appeared as well. And that's usually a planet. And that planet event only takes about an hour or two. So we really need this 50 minute cadence to characterize these events well. And also get that full two months of baseline so we can see the whole microlensing event. All right. There we go. And in order to have a lot of these events occur, you need a really high sell them: density, so the galactic way is the perfect way to look. You can see the crazy level of cloudiness here in the image here. And that is what Roman will be observing. So this survey is predicted to find approximately 1400 planets with orbital separation from two to ten AU and masses from larger than deep Jupiter down to Mars. And so, this will be the first sort of survey or large survey of planet population data be sensitive to solar system analogs. We can potentially detect all of the social system planets except for Mercury and potentially even detect some moon mass object. And you can see that towards the bottom here. In addition to that, there are these planets and bound systems but the server will also be sensitive to free-floating planets. So we've detected so few of

these objects, but it's really hard to estimate exactly how much will be detected in the Roman survey. But it is projected that we will find between 300 to 3,000 free-floating planet event in this microlensing survey. And while the survey will be providing demographics of social system analogs, the same data has been a bit providing planet detections and we have ever seen before. So with 50 minute cadence of tens of millions of stars for many months, -- excuse me -- carried out. We will be able to detect 60 to 200,000 transiting planets around a wide range of stereotypes and planet sizes. That is more than an order of magnitude in the planets we know of today. And so, also the number of planets detected in such a heavily dependent on them that elicited the of the planets occurring within the lens. So, just to show this in a slightly different way, here's the expected distance distribution for the different sizes and planets on the left, indifference to the types in the middle, and different regions of the galaxy on the right. So not only with the survey find tens of thousands of planet in the galactic bulge, but also planets on the far side of the galaxy. In addition, most of the small planets that are found will be in within five killer six of us. Which makes the follow-up with a amazing. So here's just a combined expected yield of the Roman galactic bulge time domain survey from transits and microlensing. This will allow us to both protect social system analogs as well as provide more than we've ever detected before, so it's really gonna planet science. But that is not the only revolutionary exoplanet science that women can give us. It can also test planet occurrence rate -- which is largely been forgotten due to some of the failures of the previous study. But the huge view can insert images and entire clusters all at once. And now our knowledge of occurrence rate entrance from Kepler means that we can basically step up our cluster server again. And better choose which clusters to look at. And if it works, there's lots of potential for additional studies for planets in the custody with both JWST and the Roman astrophysics surveys. So within a couple of degrees of the proposed survey, additional Roman plantings could cover all of the few in them that Ridge rich and therefore potential planet a house in our galaxy. So here I have highlighted the clusters nearest to the center. In one of those clusters is less than 2 degrees away and can capture both the Meadow Ridge and the more typical globular culture near the middle. But in the same moment planting. So thanks to previous surveys with ground-based telescopes. One lodge of the Roman and the limiting magnitude around three magnitudes fainter, based on 35,000 stars, which is the same number as the previous failed surveys, they found that many stars around these two metal rich clusters that have highlighted in the galactic bulge. If we can observe these clusters, even a half "of a cadence, and even for one season a set of six, that is still almost 10,008 met ten times the previous survey and that meets planet detection three times more likely. Not mentioning the Roman are an F will be better will have probably more stars in the actually be close this Meadow listing. Putting it all together, one season of time domain observations of one of these metal rich globular clusters can determine whether planet occurrence in these clusters stresses the Kepler field are inconsistent and a greater than three signature level for the first time. So they should be really exciting, and I yes I think it be a great thing for a moment to look at. In another sort of core community survey, Roman is also going to be doing some eggs and planet science. So the passage survey is predicted to just predict -- Roman is going to survey a hundred times the amount of sky and so they're going to increase this year to millions of in the high latitude area survey. In the time domain survey should detect these things out to five killer parsecs or more. You can also detect things like dusty up a polluted white doors in the survey. To start to understand the final stages of planet evolution. In addition,

another survey that has been proposed for women to do to better understand exoplanet is a temple survey. A survey predicted to find around a hundred and 50 exoplanet that are less than 10 million years old, in a similar number of XO satellites. These are objects that are old breeding ground dwarves or beths in the Orion nebula cluster. And this would be a great thing that they could just build on. And you can use date W-2 look at the execution of sites found in the survey. In addition we can visit other clusters. So clusters like 47 or NGC 5762 which are much more metal full then the other I mentioned, these planets are large there are hundreds of thousand in individual planets observed. It can reveal differences between clusters related to the unique chemical patterns. So the old age of these clusters will also inform the client planets in time. So you can imagine connecting this with the temple survey can show how planet occurrence change with the function of age. So in summary, both JWST and Will Mobley rapidly expand our knowledge in the system. It was JWST does this in a wide range of these nearby planetary system. Roman will expand its reach halfway across the galaxy detecting planets in ways that can never be done with such large numbers before. So together JWST Emma Grome and will put planet demographics in the galactic contest. Thank you for listening and I will take your questions.

Thank you. We have any questions online? Or any from the audience? High hi, there, great talk. Could you talk a little bit more about how you plan to detect free-floating planets that are not bound to their stars, I don't work in Exoplanet, salt, it just seems a bit impossible to me. Yes but it is not impossible, basically the idea is that you do microlensing events, but imagine instead of having a lings or lung source as well as extra blips on top of it, that instead you only have one underlying effect did but it's reduced to something that planet has. So when you detect this free-floating planets are getting the same sort of Ashley Reddick are small and because of the free-floating planet that is smaller but that depends on the geometric interactions they can actually detect this free-floating wellness objects. Before any of the questions from the audience? Thank you, great talk, my question is I didn't follow along quite well with how you can use microlensing the transits -- could you please talk a little bit about that? Sure so what I will say is that the detections of microlensing and transits will be completely different. But the idea is that using the same data set you can do both sets of the studies. And so essentially by taking 50 meeting cadence of these very stellar Richfield or the sort of two to three month seasons, get into tech these microlensing events but also for all of these scholars you get a light curve where you can sort of detected transit event instead of the typical transit approach. In so using the same data set you are actually getting -- by analyzing different link curves, you can get both these microlensing planets in these transit system in the same data. Okay thank you. Before anyone questions why there is this detected I believe he said between 1.42. something -- is there a theoretical reason between the solids and gas? Yes that's basically exactly it. This has to do with how planets form. So essentially if a planet or the planetary court does not reach a certain mass, it's never going to be able to ask for gas its surroundings. So it stays limited at the slightly larger than Earth size but is basically a rocky planet. Once you ten or 30 Earth masses -- I'm not in on this -- but basically what you get to a higher mass that he can actually start to secrete the gas that is around that planetary court. So that turned what would be sort of a Earth radius planet into something that is larger like two or three radii, then the other processes over time I can then evaporate back to being a rocky planet, basically, you always have a habit it just

depends on how close you are to the host on things like that. So I end up with this Pat Connolly of planets when you see these two gaps between two. space Laura Graytok. I was curious on the free-floating planet. I'm curious about how were going to find the free-floating planets -- I was looking at mass times Sinai or some other factors that going to be really annoying to this tangle. Because even though we see the same readings were trying to look at those entities. Yes, so for free-floating planets, I think basically with some sort of mass ratio will also the geometric probability. So to be really difficult to get masses for a lot of those objects but we estimate again from the amplitude of the microlensing effect, but it is going to be for the masses. So we will require some sort of follow-up. If something like JW -- you can imagine you do a sort of image of all of the stars are some subset of the star within the bubble taking get an overall stellar mass range, a radius range. But I think for these individual systems can be difficult we can be limited to these population level analysis of what the masses of these objects will be. Okay. Let us think again on speaker. [Applause] Thank you. Thank you again.

Nestor Espinoza: Exoplanet characterization synergies between JWST and Roman

Next speaker today is Nestor Espinoza and talking about planet exploration. Think it's very exciting to be here. The talk by Sam was great I don't have to explain in detail now, I can just get into business. So, what I'm trying to tell you in these next 10 minutes is that it is not only on finance itself but actually passing from one site to the which which is pretty so, you know this number you've already heard it. It there about 5,000 exoplanet. This can be old news in ten years. Continues this can it be like a hundred thousand. I don't know how were going to create a lot but I'll leave that to my colleagues. There are doing a focus on this planet -- so here you can have an opportunity to characterize from the detail. I think this can be pretty exciting. One important factor heavily pointed out is that most of these exoplanet than to be transiting. Maybe for some of you -- most of them will be transiting exit planet. Over a ton of opportunities -- start with unity saw from San that was obtained -- but seeing the fact that when planets transit -- if he over the different wavelengths, you will see that a planet is logically deeper in this because something is observed in the atmosphere right? Any you see this with Frank -- he sees this beautiful section as Sam is already highlighted in this is going to be the standard now. And I'm pretty envious right now. In discovering this -- it's much more complex than we previously thought. And as different from what we were expecting. And this highlights the fact that we need to keep looking at the teachers in these atmospheres. How does this compare to Roman? This than the observed into lenses. Most of them gonna happen in the 1.46 microns. Like a one night got them more or less. And then .87 microns. And as you can see here, the Roman F146 marks all the water cultures. All these water features that your scene. The chances that Roman is been observed. and they both started continue. So in theory you should able to see the blip with one wavelength and the other. Let me show you an example. So Roman is going to look at the tens and thousands of exoplanets which is exciting. So here we're showing you the same similar 39 spectrum I showed you before. But it's got some oil and some water. And they Mark Geist to form Roman. One is larger than the other just because of the water feature. In the sense is this teacher depends on how cloudy the exoplanet is. It is very cloudy and it will be very similar. If the planet has no clouds, then it will be very, very different. No clouds in the planet that texts change. While it is going to be very difficult to Roman to just detect the split in one planet, they

can play by the number. they do not have enough planet new can it be able to see the planets together and form it properly. Is an example of being on 30 planets from when I just mentioned. And they'll be able to detect the water feature in the little population for just a chance how cool is that? And the incredible thing is that for the brightest of the brightest star, Roman is going to detect, you could follow-up with -- and is pretty feet and from the bright end of Roman -- but just a single chance you can see from the images here before and the CO2. So my college years for the Roman folks that getting that sweet and bright photography -- we really want to see them. Because they could actually link the two and follow-up this very special planet that Roman is discovering. Okay, so, basically these planets offer you a clips when a planet passes behind it and that's a pretty exciting feature because as I just told you, the mean -- survey is going to have these wanted to Mike Rohn Bank. And we do not have a lot of wanted to Mike Rohn a clips is out there. The only people getting those eclipses come from the old -- and they've exhausted all those targets. And I have room in this grenade enable you to get in a clips of thousands of those planets. So that is a new science. So what can we do? Well let me show you one. These were seen a couple of months ago. So you can get basically the same thing executrix showed you. The macular feature but it's very different to the transit were looking in the region and the think event in the morning in the evening of the planet. And here you are looking at other side. And you have a well simple as a clips and you can actually study the light and that can show you how the light is around that baseline. And it's based on -- but they have some sort of curvature and that means the planet is this team and it appeared that tell you so I can actuallyHere is the simulation that we did for the four day orbit. I'm focusing here on the little eclipse, it seems small -- is not one of the blip that happens when the planet passes behind the star which is basically protecting the photons from the planet but when the plaintiff goes up, you're seeing the phases of the planet like you see the faces of the moon, you could do the same with the faces of the exoplanets and we can do this for thousands of worlds out there. It's more than a thousand, as a factor of a thousand, more... From one to make 200. From space we definitely don't have these wavelengths. That little snitch between one and 2 microns, we don't but enrollment is going to get you. It doesn't have to be centered around the secondary eclipse, that phase shift also tells you information about the nature of the planets, we will be able to get this. What can you get from eclipses? You can get a lot. The time of secondary eclipse depends on the eccentricity of the orbit, on the actual orbit and you could get that information. You can get redistribution properties if this phase shift happens for certain planets but not for others, that means something is happening. People have been claiming this for a little while now, you can see many faces, it might be changes in time, now you're going to have thousands of worlds to explore that same thing, a very nice baseline that woman looks at. To conclude on everything I'm trying to tell you, these emerging results are definitely modifying new frontiers on exit plan of science. Roman is going to get you that ended in terms of exit planet characteristics, the fact that Roman has been observed and gets used so many exome planets, it can help you -- automations might not achieve. Finally, Roman might be synergistic and couple meant, not only for sciences, bright objects with Roman, can you enlarge that? Please?

Questions in the room? You talk a lot about atmospheres surface composition and thermal inertia, what is the expected amount of exoplanets you could do this sort of study with and gain atmosphere exome planets? That was tried with Kepler. For the smallest planets, the Roman

position on a single planet would be enough to detect the eclipse you can stack the eclipses from different small worlds and try to form a super eclipse -- this was tried with Kepler, the wavelengths Kepler was looking at made it very hard. Roman has two things in its favor, wavelengths and numbers. You're going to have tens of thousands of exome planets that you can actually scale and form those super layers. That's science you can expect Other questions in the room? In theory you could go above Neptune? Stacking you can go smaller. If there are no questions, thanks to the speaker. Thank you. [Applause] Can you hear me?

Julien Girard: Finding planets with Roman and JWST

The next speaker is speaking of finding exoplanets with Roman and JWST. Good afternoon, I hope you're not sleeping. I know a lot of you are not exoplanet experts, it's going to be helpful to me to have this amount of energy -- now I'm going to talk about finding exoplanets with imaging techniques because other techniques have been mostly covered. By now you know we have found a lot of planets, mostly with transiting and radial velocity approaches. They are everywhere, different type of compositions that present like ones we have in the solar system. Planets a little bit bigger than Earth that we don't have in the solar system but we find a good Jupiters but we also don't have in our solar system. The different techniques by now you know most of them. They have been described already, I'm going to focus on those two, mainly the one in the middle, the direct imaging which is also called high contrast imaging and one big advantage of it is you see, you detect directly the photons of the planet and in this case for example four big, young Jupiters, a scaled up version of our solar system, you can see them moving, we can observe those planets with JW ST as well except the data is not public yet. The S to astrometry is looking at the orbit, informing direct imaging campaigns. This is a figure that was just crafted today and we have been asking for it because I couldn't find it, where is the chronograph instrument view with respect to the huge instrument view in the focal plane of Roman was Mike you see the detectors the instruments, that would be the size of the moon. This little blue dot here is the detector of the chronograph instrument, as a technology demonstrator, its aim is to show him you can control in space, you can fly electron multiplying CCDs and also that you can reach a contrast that allows you to do a giant planet in reflected light, just like you see Jupiter in the night sky or around other stars. That is for real, the chronograph instrument as we speak, some elements here. Not going to put too much details, you have seen this several times before. We have been able to image directly so far, of course they are separation, around 1 to 1015 Jupiter masses. They are basically big Jupiters, we don't have the sensitivity even with JW ST. With JW ST we can go down a little bit in contrast -- we are going to keep doing this -- we are going to be able to go down in mass to see planets with 40-meter telescopes. We are going to tackle this fragment of space, then the Roman chronograph will be here trying to find Jupiter may be down to Neptune mass in reflected light. And of course some speculative platforms I hope to see in my career. From the ground there are surveys that have been done, a lot of disks have been found and in some cases I would say a couple handfuls of cases, we found some planetary mass objects, we can draw diagrams like this, some diagram I don't know how you call it. JWST and the Roman chronograph, we don't have enough time, it's very time-consuming to get high contrast, we cannot go fishing like that. We have to go after informed targets, it's a bit more like fly-fishing. You see the fish, you try to

get it and the formation, you get it from astrometry. You know it's a trend in proper motion. It's a planet from radial velocity with large time-based lines. You see what is found this way, basically able to detect its photons. Also a flip was detected like that. To put it simply, this is what we can do today. When they are actually accreting for the first time, JWST allowed us to find a micron. Before 2030, we should be able to do reflected light. It's not that much time, if it works hopefully there will be a general observer. Beyond the 20, hopefully we have a bigger mission -- that is going to be reflected light in the optical and the goal here is to go after a few earthlike planets. Our colleagues in Europe do the same type of planets but in thermal meeting for it. This is the road map, this is how the data looks like. The real data from JWST, the plaintiff has just been renamed by the community. It's an example of how the data is going to look like on the small field of view on the Roman photograph, one Jupiter mass each. On the right is hopefully tend to make a 15-meter telescope would see if it is to fly in the future. The way it works for JWST, this is a simulation preflight when the mass is in front of, it's actually not enough to see planets like Jupiter, you basically have to subtract a separate star. Works very well, just to mimic a planet about 10,000 contrast. A few days later in July of last year, we got those six wavelengths with two instruments. It was discovered in 2017, the first time from space in this image. JWST has a bit of a beam size issue, the wavelength is bigger. If you were to go after, that's how it would look. It has been done but I cannot show you today. It is tremendously sensitive and stable, but the beam size is a little bit bigger. I'm going to stop here because I'm running out of time, but this is super exciting. The Roman chronograph in cement is a stepping-stone to go beyond with a big telescope and it is our best shot as a community to get planets in reflected light by the end of this decade. Thank you.

Do we have questions from the audience? Surprise from Roman, maybe I'm going to show a few slides. The expectation from the Roman chronograph, there's a requirement that has been relaxed, we know it's easy to achieve with respect to the hardware we have. You basically have murals that are controlled with calculations made on the ground and sent to the spacecraft, everything has to be very stable. Everything works well, this is the requirement, if it's here, maybe instead of doing giant planets like Jupiter we can go down a little bit in mass. I'm not talking about it here because I said it was finding planets but it's also critical after a few disks. One problem we have is we have a ton of galaxies popping out. With Roman chronograph, it might be in some case a surprise. Between now and then, hopefully that is going to keep on analyzed and released and we will have some really good candidates very nearby. Hopefully we can go ten to the minus nine. In the meantime may be an online question? Sure. I have a question online -- why is there no plans for a star shade instead of a chronograph for Roman? I think this is a little bit above my pay grade may be. [Laughter] I think maybe you can answer better than me. For the data challenge, I didn't show many slides here, we made the transit, one that will fly and two with the staff shade which I think is still possible but not decided, maybe not likely -- I don't know. The star shade was an idea that floated around for a long time for Roman, but it became apparent at some point that a star shade was not going to be developed and ready in time for the chronograph to use it because the chronograph is not designed to be in in cement that necessarily will last the full lifetime. We have made choices that would make it extremely problematic to try to cooperate with a star shade at this point. I hope that answers the question. Yeah. It could be added in the future though. In detail to operate with a star shade, you

don't merely have to have a dark thing floating out in space that you stare at, you have to coordinate the motions of those things, that requires hardware on both the Roman side and the star shade side, the hardware doesn't exist on the Roman side so yes, it is possible that someone would have to go up there and service woman to do it. My question is is there any prospect of direct imaging planets of the Widefield? I had this slide also, there is a way to have synergy between the two I think, this has been studied in 2018, there is mention of it in the 2020 white paper. If you take a single epic on a bright star and do exquisite astrometry using all the diffraction spikes, you may reach a single position of something like 15 microseconds. That would be very useful to anchor and extend the acceleration measurements beyond the mission lifetime, also get more of those informed targets, which would be for the chronograph and also high contrast imagers. Also you can use those to do a better job and kept the position those planets. That was my conclusion. The Roman chronograph introduces a new contrast regime, giant planets in reflected light, it's the main thing the main demonstration. Both of those benefits from exoplanetary systems. The question is Roman the first major mission to utilize the chronograph in this way? It's the first space mission that will have murals on board to perform control in space. Underground we do have optics to get basically extreme what we call diffraction limited beam from which you can separate the star and the planet. In space you can affect a thousand or so better, correct the defects of all the optics and also the spacecraft has a bit of a heat transfer happening. You need to be stable over hours. Thanks again to the speaker.

Pedro Rodriguez DeSilva: Eta Tel B, 20 years of follow up

The next speaker is Pedro Rodriguez DeSilva. [Laughter] Okay, it's on. Thank you everyone for this opportunity to present my work. I'm a PhD student in my last year, at the end of the year I will be hunting for postdoc. I'm going to tell you about what my group is doing about systems characterization. Thanks to Julian, I don't need to spend too much time on that slide because basically we are using high contrast imaging and you can see in the plot, the green circles show the planets that have been detected which are massive and we can extend to larger separations from the primary sources than other planetary detection techniques. With high contrast imaging, we have observed some interesting objects and systems, for example we have observed planets forming not just with activation but with our observations and a lot of things, we can see planets forming, we also have this gift that Julian presented of HR 8799, we have detected planets in a similar system and we also have detected systems composed by a center star and two stellar objects. Combining all of that with what we know about the star systems, we can imagine okay, if we are observing the primary source like a very bright star, it can be a brown dwarf, it can be a planet, it is possible to find something surrounding this, the answer is theoretically yes. But it's hard to find it, because we need to suppress not just the light from the primary source but also the companion, it's a very challenging and the processing, in the instrumental part. That is instrument in length, the better fit for this. And based on the instruments response, we tracked that from the observation. We can obtain some sort of -- if there is something, some sort of -- let's not use the word excellent, it can be contrary but a satellite or a planetary disk forming. In that same post she found the first satellite candidate -- okay. We have the survey, so basically just briefly it will give us more, that will improve our subtraction. They started observation I think three days ago, we don't have the data yet but with that we can go

deeper trying to find something you can see it is a very massive one, which is good because it is bright. So, so, it, we can detect like it is well separated from the star. It is not polluted by this mask of the system. And we can see what we have with the old sphere observation that we cannot see really here because we need deeper -- so, another reason why we are doing this there is data. The stable has all the published data with the positions. Here, I'm showing separation and position angle. This doesn't contain three points using, it doesn't have the ongoing survey will add one more point. We have a lot of coverage, that we can do and follow-up. On the right, you can see the contrast curves obtained by the oldest sphere observation. And we will improve that with deeper observation of this. You may be thinking, why am I talking about this it is not with Roman, it's because we are doing the maximum to the length observations, but we are aiming to go for spatial telescopes. With this coverage, we can do preliminary results using ORVARA. We can see the time from position angle and separation. We can also predict the location of the companion in real time. And also ORVARA allows radial velocity data. Which we don't have at the moment. But, we have the data, pointing towards the companion, and we have ongoing survey with CRIFES plus that tells us the first, radial velocity, and our companion. So, we are working on that also, and with RV data, we can monitoring to look for satellite, which I mean we can see an example here. Use it -- our ongoing, we have just one but we are, we will possibly, obtain all of the ones that we requested. Until the end of the year. With the RV diagonal, we can see something is perturbing the planet in the bottom middle plot we can see what would be this signal for it. And we have preliminary results. We have the temperature of the companion. Summarizing, we are doing data and orbital characterization of Tel B, more than 20 years of data. We are doing the first ever high-resolution Spectra of an HCl, the first satellite hunting around the source. And we are proving the contrast curves. Not just from this object, but for other objects in our sample. Well, so, in this contrast I'm talking about a lot of sphere but we are aiming to use spatial telescopes that are more suitable to the task. So we can see this table here, it specifications from James Webb, on the right, we can see a comparison of contrast of grace Roman and with the spear. In a sphere, we typically have -5 and -6 contrast but with Grace Roman we can have up to four. So magnitude, more sensible to find anything. This is great, not just -- but for all people that can, it is interesting to trace some sort of signal around these. With that, you can update our symmetry and characterization of the objects and improve the curves and satellites. I will leave you with the face of our team. In the first row, -- second row of the data scientists. The group asks you to stay tuned for future publications. Thank you.

Thank you. We don't have questions online. Is anybody in the room that wants to ask a question? You mentioned you're working also another system, the size of the sample. So, the first sample is 25 objects. But in the ongoing sphere survey, with more depth, we are serving 15. 15, are their companions? Or -- the mass of the sample? The mass of the sample, I think it goes from the Exoplanet I'm not sure but -- A question over there. This is probably pretty basic question but again, Exoplanets are not my thanks piece of the term exo can be problematic? No, first we were using the word but part of that community does not accept it too much because it is, I mean, the candidate is one mass. We think a solar system, you do not think like something big. We were just considering the mass range because -- the mass would be similar

of a moon here but still, it is not the size and the mass of the moon. It is problematic term. Any more questions? Thank you again to the speaker.

Rosemary Pike: Discovery and characterization of small bodies in the Solar System

The next up is an online presentation. It will be her on the screen. Thanks. So, I am Rosemary E. Pike at the Center for astrophysics. I will be talking about solar system stuff. Discovery and characterization of small bodies in the solar system. Looking at some results and prospects for Roman. It is a mix of unpublished and published results from database T and I want to give special thanks to some of those that provided plots and results for this talk. To start off with, basically as a general overview, we have small bodies in the solar system which formed in a disk, it evolved over four geeky years. Through collisions, scattering and movement by planets. And all of that resulted in the small bodies that we see today. A lot of different populations and they have a couple of different characteristics. That we study to try and understand all of these processes. When you look at size distribution of the current objects, how many big things or small things. We look at composition, what they're made of. We look at their shapes, dynamics and orbit distribution of the objects. The fundamental question we are trying to answer is, what do we see today? And how do we use it to learn about the formation of the solar system for small body characteristics. I'm basically going to start in the inner solar system, and work my way out with all of these small rocky bodies. And so, just to make sure we are all in sync. Should we start with sort of a near Earth object population which is *, near Earth comments. This is asteroid Eros. these have orbits near the earth. Can potentially be hazardous, so these can be powerful impactors and part of my job at the center is to try to find, to help complete orbits and for those who find all of these asteroids. As move outward we have asteroid belt, including dwarf planets in the asteroid belt such as Ceres. this is a pretty large population which is really cool originally involved due to various object planet scattering. As we go further out, we have the natural satellites of the giant planets be there two different types of satellites. They regular size and irregular satellites. This is a picture of Europa, these are sort of larger bodies that are in a disk kind of like what we have around there were so system and the planets. Some have irregular satellites that are thought to be captured. A lot of these objects, they are high -- much farther from the planet. They sample an entire different history of formation and evolution the knees satellites. As move for the out, we get to this region where we have Cleto and Eros. This is an image of Pluto and the moons. Before the new horizons encounter. All of these objects form what we call the trans Neptunian objects. This is beyond Neptune is orbit. This is to build where to focus my research. Beyond that we have the word cloud. This is a big spherical region. There are no clouds of observed in the cloud. The only way we see them is when they come in as comments. Often, they come in as retrograde comments. So comedies, severely different characteristics than those that come from other belt to evolve into more low inclination events. Just in summary, we are looking at sort of all of these different properties of the small bodies today. We tried to use it to infer history in the formation and evolution. What do we specifically learn from small bodies using JWST? We start the Eller system again, you may have seen some of the press releases related to dart which was impact mission, it was a an intentional crash into a 190 meter orbit object. Which was -- when the impact occurred we saw a tight claim of material with wisps away from the center. And it was image with the near cam

imager. The idea with this impactor was to try to change the orbit, over a period of the moon lit this could be well measured to the series of mutual events and between the primary and secondary. This object was selected basically as a test of planetary defense systems in the future, like if we have a future impact or we know how hitting an object would actually change its orbital properties. So, they found that the impact slowed the rotation of the more false by 33 minutes, which is more than they expected. A really successful test. One of the things that we really exciting and forthcoming in the ure, is the NIRSpec data and NIRCam data that can provide information about what it ctually was d because knowing what the material is composed of, can help us understand the material strength of these of these objects. And how they might respond impact in general. Very exciting asteroid. I included some results here from serendipitous asteroid observations. This is particularly relevant to Roman. Basically, this is a JWST MIRI image taken for a science case it was not asteroid related. Have two asters in the frame. You can see multiple positions the asteroid moving and subtraction. There are smaller asteroids detectable using JWST, then general asteroid surveys. Certainly, in these wavelengths. One of these objects was known and will was not previously known. There will be a huge serendipitous catalog of asteroids found, both with JWST and later with Roman. Which provides the data we need to calculate a large catalog of sizes and albedos and possibly new discoveries. Those move outward into the main asteroid belt. This is a main belt comment. Main belt comments are really unusual. We think about cometary activity is typically objects coming from the outer solar system which possess lots of all tiles and as a get heated by the sun, everything sublimates and it causes these beautiful tales, and lots of all tiles. But in the main belt region, we expect these objects to be pretty devoid of these volatile. Because a been a much warmer place. A lot of times, it seems likely activity in this region is triggered by collisions. It is also possible that these could be interlopers from the outer solar system that just look like they're currently made out of asteroids. This particular object, is comment read and the bluntness a pretty typical comment. You can see what is really important, is that with the blue spectra we see both waters and carbon dioxide relatively similar proportions. Ratio of water to carbon dioxide is often used to measure how many well tiles are in a comet. But, when we look at this comet Read we see no carbon docs or whatever. The way this is interpreted, is basically that this is not a interloper. From a more distant orbit, or expect preservation of carbon dioxide. This is the first ever detection of water omission in a main belt comment . While using dust and activity, we've never just detected that before James Webb. This detection of water is really important for our understanding of what the asteroids are made of. If there are a large number of asteroids actually have subsurface water ice that is preserved long-term, it will greatly change our understanding of how water ice is preserved in the solar system and possibly, even how water came to earth. And so, this is a really exciting discovery. And hopefully, we are followed by more spectra of main belt comets and we can also expect Roman to discover a good number of main belt comets, which can be targeted for follow-up with JWST, searching for these emission water and carbon dioxide emissions. Right. And this is the plot of the carbon dioxide to water ratio. For a lot of different comets. Basically, just want to reiterate, how unusual this main belt comet is compared to all the other comments we have seen. Basically, it is this red dot , the basic red upper limit. There are no known comets that look like this. These main belt comets are really, really exciting. And probably change how we understand the asteroid belt in general. One of the other really interesting results has come from Enceladus. this is one of the moons of

Saturn. It is found in basically, a force of water particles. Which is emitting itself from plumes. There was a large plume observed coming from Enceladus at cryogenic temperatures and they found that it was similar to Casini and the Torus density is consistent with previous Herschel observations. Look like basically, the water production rate is relative long-term. And a huge ring around Saturn. And interestingly, even with the with the sensity of JWST they'll have water ice, no carbon dioxide or carbon monoxide. They also found basically water ice on the desk of Enceladus where was dominant in crystalline form. Previously, they found carbon dioxide on the surface and lack of detection is probably a geometric effect. Because it is near the poles. Long-term monitoring of the surface of Enceladus and other moons, can also help us understand the composition of a lot of the major planets. Now, we are getting into the outer solar system, and taking a look at Centaurs, these are the population of objects evolving from the region into sort of the family comet region so these objects have orbits inward of say Neptune but outward of Jupiter. And there is quite a range of different things that we see. And a lot of these objects actually have jets. Some of them have rings. One with rings is -- the rings were not before this was observed from JWST. You can see the basically, the NIRCcam imaging on the right pretty to see how much starlet is blocked. The occultation on will be on the rings and not behind the main artery which is where we see those two quick productions in the light from the star. But, they are two rings around the spirit partially resolved in this. Which was October 2022. There will be a lot of work in the future, looking at this carefully, to try to understand how the rings form and how long-term stable they are. So, it is one of the things that most likely, the rings are composed of particles that are water ice from the surface of Charliklo. And another body that collide with Charliklo in the past. We don't expect the rings to last forever. It is a question, the rings uniformly thick all around Charliklo, and what is the size of the particles, and what does it tell us about the frequency of impacts and the hyper belt? So, there's a lot of ongoing work here and trying to better understand how the outer solar system is currently evolving, and what causes these ring systems in the Centaurs. To trying to understand this a little better, here is actually, the surface of Charliklo. It is dominated by water ice signatures. So, previous ground-based spectra has really struggled to identify surface ice. Partly because the wavelength coverage and partly because these objects are faint. A lot of the features are recently broad. On the left, there are some of the best spectra from the literature. You can see particularly in 2003 may be, there are hints of water ice and also, in 2013, we could see hints of crystalline water ice in the spectra. But really, it is a real challenge to identify features from the ground. But once we move up to JWST, you can see these really clear water ice absorption bands. In multiple positions along the spectra, and also there is not a whole else in this object in particular. And so, I'm about to show a whole bunch of small body surface spectra. You should keep in mind for all of them, pretty much that most of the ground has been taken -- featureless except some dwarf planets. Then we mostly just see like a featureless line at varying degrees of slope. Not much omission or sloping. So, as you move a little bit out from the centaurs, we have 1 to 1 residents of Neptune. In the 1 to 1 residents, there are some very interesting, basically the sample is very unusual. The objects we usually refer to them based on their optical colors. The neutral red, red, very red, ultra-red and all these objects and the optical are red. In this region we have a pretty big mix of these red and ultra-red surfaces. In the 1 to 1, Neptune rsonance is one known object that has us ultra-red color. And so, this is a project where they took spectra, most of the known Neptune Trojans and tried to compare the one

particular ultra-red object to the red objects, and figure out how those compared to the other objects. The fundamental question is, why do the distribution of surfaces and Trojans look so different from what we see in the -- region. Spectra really is going to be big key for understanding these, whether the composition has evolved since the objects have come to the Trojan region, or whether this is basically just a sample size issue. Or has to do with say, size of the objects because the closer and, the objects are commonly different, the smaller the detections are. Here, you can see JWST spectra , the ultra-red object has this kind of similar to the Triton , which is radiated organic model . The red objects show strong water ice feature and reddening. This is also, pretty much what we see in the TNOS region. That analysis is ongoing. But, it will be really exciting to see, it does look like they are similar to the TNOS and is a bit of an open question as to why the ratio is so different in Neptune Trojan . Just for fun, here are some beautiful dwarf planet spectra. This is Eris. we say lot that we don't see him smaller bodies. And here we have some dark objects. So, Eros is the highest object in the solar system. It is Jim -- geometric. These look different. As opposed to be dominated by nitrogen and methane, have a bunch of organic material on the surface. Organics haven't really been detected this clearly from the ground. In particular, it has been near impossible to identify what organic materials actually around the surface of TNOS. Modeling of organic materials in the spectrum is all still ongoing but organics are clearly detected. As well as water and carbon dioxide. This is a spectra from a midsized resident object. Similar to Charon in size. It is selected basically based on similarity to Charon because we have observations in the system. The preliminary reduction of this object shows water, ice, carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide. The detection of carbon monoxide of TNOS is really new to JWST. A little bit low on time. But just to summarize all of these TNOS service modeling, we have a very large parameter 96 hours. This targeted 59 TNOs to look at their spectra. Looking all different orbits and the range of sizes that are typically, that we typically already know. And they find both crystalline and amorphous water ice and detected them in four groups per the critical thing about these four groups, is that they are based on the shape of the water ice absorption and carbon dioxide absorption. And they correlate with the optical colors. As analysis moves forward with this, really hopeful that we will be able to tell the optical colors to this, to the volatile populations in the objects. That is really interesting to see, people been classifying the based on their optical colors for a long time because that is what is available. But to see these really clear based on volatile ice has been really exciting. This is results from a TNOS discovery survey about 45 hours. Looking at a pencil beam survey where they are trying to find moving objects. On the left, you can see one of the images, then a stack, on the right, that is image with a removed and you consider very faint little object right there that is a TNO. that when his previous name known. This is about 30 classical TNOs with them is down to 10 kilometers. Much smaller than any previous survey to date. And getting the number of objects down to a small size, really helps understand how the outer solar system objects formed. What was the formation mechanism for the outer solar system. And this is particularly relevant for Roman because this type of search, is probably how we would find most of the objects that we will be discovering in the Roman survey. So, here, I will touch on some Roman stuff. Roman science cases. Sorry, I just have a few minutes, but we have a couple of really exciting things that we haven't been able to do from other facilities. Some of which can be done through the general surveys. Some of which may be requiring additional surveys. Additional project spirit finding earth Trojans is one of the things it

is really hard to do from the air for geometric reasons. These are points of the earth orbit and can actually be stable for the age of the solar system. There are only two known, but we could actually discover hundreds of objects with the Roman telescope in the Trojan points. Another really exciting population we can discover a lot of things and is the high inclination Centaurs. When we search for solar system objects, people tend to search along the ecliptic plane because that's where most of the objects are pretty far the most things if you look for the most where they are poor but we are biased against finding this the leader off of that plane and hyphenation Centaurs are dominated by the cloud publishes finding incoming cloud objects. It is something really great to understand better. And so, particularly the high latitude surveys, to discover a lot of retrograde Centaurs and other high inclination objects pretty high inclination objects also really sensitive to additional masses in the solar system. An additional massive planet, or additional discs, basically additional belts that might exist out beyond that belt. Roman is also ideal for an irregular satellite search of giant planets. I mentioned really that irregular satellites are captured and we can get a good idea of the size distribution of these distant populations by looking at the size distribution of these irregular satellites. Right now, the hill spheres probably about 50 percent complete in terms of whether we know how many things are in them, and we can actually get to smaller sizes. In previous surveys down to about five kilometers. Or 11 kilometers, depending. Neptune and, really you only need, you need about 100 -- dependent which of the giant planets are trying to fill the giant Hill sphere of. The wide field of view gives us a really great way to find these irregular satellites. We also may discover a lot of comets, and interstellar objects. Finding possible interstellar objects as a pastor the field of view. That was pretty straightforward. And then, finding this quickly, so we can do characterization, it would be hugely impactful science. And my own personal favorite thing is, this discovery of TNOs in the surveys. Enhanced discoveries if a ecliptic spur is included in some of these high latitude wide field surveys. And if the broadband filters use you can find smaller things. We also get serendipitous characterizations. I've talked about the Roman filters on the upper left there. You can see it cover some of the water ice, but also, some of the optical, where as we discussed previsit, optical colors are correlated with the surface type. Discovering a large number of TNOs given them into bands and selecting which was to follow up with detailed JWST spectroscopy would provide a great data set for better understanding the populations. And so, in summary, the JWST results for solar system bodies are just beginning. But the identification of different volatile is providing a really great context for interpreting the surface data we have been seeing for years. We expect Roman to serendipitously characterize known bodies in the solar system. Thank you. Speaker ?

We have time for questions from the audience or online? Any questions from the audience? Statistic is hard to do because we only know two but how many interstellar objects would you hope to see? Yet, it is really hard to speculate, right? Because we found two. They were completely different! One of them was like a typical what we would expect of say, a TNO in the solar system or a comet. And the other will look completely different. One speculates it is nitrogen ice. Yet, I would hate, yeah, I guess I'm not really comfortable speculating. But I do think that, that it is not unreasonable to expect you know, more than one per year. Something like that. But there are so many different assumptions you could make. And then of course, it depends on what wavelengths as well. And whether they are active, right? If it becomes active,

we can detect things that are much smaller. What about the number of estimated earth Trojans? Care to speculate on that? Yeah, so, based on the current models. Which again, are based on two. We would expect there could be hundreds that we would discover . Okay, last call for questions. There is one online, okay. Yes, isn't it also possible that the spectroscopy of the TNOs depend on the defects? If so, how improved area and wavelengths help? So, spectroscopy depending on -- so, I guess the question is, basically, are the surfaces the same at all faces, right? Is that? So, when you get spectrocity, it is one region of the surface. Most TNOs don't show variability, with the exception of some larger ones. Obviously, then there was actual surface activity like Pluto. We have ice resurfacing and stuff PC pretty large changes in surface composition. So, yeah . It is complicated to interpret say, spectrocity, taken at multiple different epics. Often, it can reflect changes in the service at different periods of time. But overall, in general, most of the distant solar system objects have the same surfaces. They rotate, which is what we see. But there is a much smaller sample of really good spectrocity . Let me know if that was not quite what you were looking for. I don't see the chart from the -- okay. I think that , is there another question? If not, I will think the speaker again.

Poster lightening talk: Arielle Moullet

Before we leave the room, we do have one presentation. We don't have the name on here. Please go ahead. I'm a staff scientist and with a few colleagues, at the North American ALMA science center, we put together this poster to remind people of how ALMA is a great instrument to follow up on detection of high z sources. There are two plots there showing how the different lines and ionized lines are detected with z -- different transition of logic can be observed at different branches. From these type of observations, one can get spectroscopic, metallicity, molecular composition, stellar dust molecular gas mass, outflow maps. This is mostly to highlight that ALMA is currently undergoing a wide array of bands that will be completed almost 10 years from now, but this has a direct impact on the research because line sensitivity will increase by 50 percent at all bands. In continuing sensitivity by 7220 percent. Look at the poster, you'll get a sense of what ALMA can do now. But, by the time Roman is up, several of the bands s will have been upgraded and the detection level, detect sensitivity, will be significantly better. If you have any question, or you want to explore how some observation could benefit your science case, powered by Roman in particular. Please do not hesitate to reach out. That is all I had. Thank you. I think this was the only one. Do we have any announcement from the organizer? Please, thank you for being here today. And enjoy the session now.

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

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